

Impact Assessment Tool in Karelia's CoARA Cascade Project

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Karelia University of Applied Sciences is developing research assessment as part of the CoARA consortium, which includes over 800 research organizations as well as key research funders. CoARA (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment) aims to reform the practices for evaluating research, researchers, and research organizations, with its main goal being to strengthen the quality and impact of research. At the same time, the focus of research assessment is shifting from quantitative evaluation toward qualitative assessment, and the diversity of research and research careers is being recognized.

Signing the CoARA agreement is a step for Karelia University of Applied Sciences towards more open, responsible, and impactful RDI (Research, Development, and Innovation) activities. The participation of universities of applied sciences in the renewal of assessment practices is important, as RDI activities at these institutions differ in many ways from that of traditional academic universities. Universities of applied sciences carry out practical development projects, applied research, and product development in cooperation with businesses and other organizations. For this reason, qualitative assessment methods that take into account the specific nature of RDI activities at universities of applied sciences are needed, so that impact can be evaluated by more than just numbers.

Karelia received project funding for developing assessment

In summer 2025, the CoARA consortium carried out its second Cascade Funding call, supporting the development of research and researcher assessment within organizations. More than 140 applications were submitted, and 28 projects received funding. Funding was granted for team projects, pilot projects, and projects aiming for sustainable changes in organizational assessment practices. Karelia received funding for the pilot project "Assessment Tool for

Evaluating the Qualitative Impact of RDI Activities at Universities of Applied Sciences.”

In Karelia’s pilot project, a tool suitable for assessing impact will be designed and implemented, to be integrated into the entire lifecycle of Karelia’s RDI projects—from planning to execution. The assessment tool helps define the desired impact goals for a project, select appropriate measures to achieve them, monitor the fulfillment of these goals, and evaluate the impact of the projects.

The project is more broadly related to developing the quality of all operations at Karelia University of Applied Sciences. Audits conducted by The Finnish Education Evaluation Centre (FINEEC) during 2018–2024 have highlighted the need to clarify the societal interaction and impact goals of higher education institutions and to develop metrics for assessing their realization. Karelia has identified a particular need for development in RDI activities, where impact assessment has become inconsistent due to the diversity of project activities, and there have been no clear processes or tools for it. Thus, assessment in projects has mainly focused on actions rather than their impact.

Responsible quantitative and qualitative assessment

The assessment tool being developed in the project is based on the recommendations of the DORA declaration (San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment) for responsible quantitative evaluation. This means that quantitative indicators are applied in the assessment as appropriate for the context. Comprehensive assessment should utilize both quantitative and qualitative indicators. The goal is to create a tool that enables systematic, holistic, and responsible assessment of RDI projects, so that the impact and effectiveness of projects can be reliably verified. To our knowledge, no similar tool is in use in other Finnish universities of applied sciences. Once completed, the tool will be openly shared for use by all organizations in both national and international CoARA networks, as well as in the Zenodo data repository.

The intent is that the RDI project assessment tool will also help identify potential biases in research and development activities. By evaluating societal impact

over the long term, it is possible to identify significant and lasting effects stemming from the RDI projects of the university of applied sciences. In addition, it is important to assess the ongoing and concrete interaction between RDI projects and companies, as these daily contacts can lead to immediate impacts and develop into significant long-term outcomes.

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